

Physiology and plant nutrition

Effect of nitrogen and zinc on indole-3-acetic acid (IAA) concentration in roots and root production in wetland rice

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IAA triggers meristematic activity and plant growth. A high IAA concentration in rice roots, especially at panicle initiation stage is indicative of high root production and activity and better crop performance.

We measured IAA concentration in rice roots at panicle initiation in relation to N and Zn nutrition at TNAU (11°N, 77°E and 427 m above sea level) during the southwest monsoon season (Jun-Sep) 1983. The factorial design combined 4 levels of N (0, 60, 90, and 120 kg N/ha) and 2 levels of Zn (0 and 5.75 kg/ha). The soil contained 1.1% organic C, 196-9.5-200 ppm available NPK, 598 ppm total soil N, and 0.4 ppm DTPA extractable Zn. Test variety was IR20. The test field was laid out in a randomized block design with six replications.

N and Zn showed a synergistic interaction on IAA concentration in rice

roots. At 120 kg N/ha with Zn, IAA in roots was highest (462 µg/kg fresh root); at 120 kg N/ha without Zn, it was very low (281 µg/kg fresh root) (Table 1). IAA concentration was more or less the same at all levels of N without Zn.

Root weight increased with N increase up to 120 kg/ha at all growth stages (Table 2). Zn also increased root production at all stages. The coefficients of correlation of IAA concentration in rice roots with root dry weight at panicle initiation (0.55), root dry weight at flowering (0.51), and root dry weight at harvest (0.56) were significant and positive. □

Table 2. Root dry weight at different growth stages as influenced by levels of N and Zn.

	Root dry weight (t/ha)			
	Tillering	Panicle initiation	Flowering	Harvest
N level (kg/ha)				
0	0.4	0.8	0.9	1.1
60	0.5	0.9	1.1	1.2
90	0.5	1.2	1.3	1.4
120	0.7	1.4	1.6	1.7
LSD (0.05)	0.05	0.1	0.1	0.1
Zn level (kg/ha)				
0	0.5	1.0	1.1	1.3
5.75	0.6	1.2	1.3	1.4
LSD (0.05)	0.04	0.09	0.08	0.06

Soil fertility and fertilizer management

Tissue test of rice plant nitrogen

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In Australia, rice farmers dry-seed rice by drill sowing directly into a dry seedbed or by drilling into a closely grazed pasture. The crop is flooded 2-4 times before it reaches the 3- to 4-leaf stage, when a permanent flood is applied. Or, fields are permanently flooded with shallow water and pregerminated rice seed is dropped by airplane.

The recommended times for N fertilizer application are just before permanent flood and just after panicle initiation. If farmers are confident of the appropriate fertilizer rate, all or most is

applied before the permanent flood. If farmers are unsure of the appropriate fertilizer rates or if there is a risk of overfertilization or low-temperature sterility, one-half to two-thirds N is applied before permanent flood, the remainder at panicle initiation.

A critical management decision is the amount of N to apply at panicle initiation to achieve maximum yield.

We have developed a plant analysis test that can rapidly determine crop N status and estimate N topdressing needed. Whole shoot samples are cut at ground level at panicle initiation, quickly dried in a 700 W microwave oven (200 g fresh wt in 13-15 min), ground in a Cyclone mill to pass through a 1-mm screen, and analyzed for tissue N status by near infrared reflectance (NIR).

NIR gave an excellent correlation with traditional Kjeldahl N analysis (see figure). Preliminary results indicate that

Table 1. N-Zn interactions on rice root IAA content at panicle initiation.^a TNAU, India, 1983.

Zn level (kg/ha)	IAA content (µg/kg fresh root)				
	No N	N60	N90	N120	Mean
0	279	283	299	281	278
5.75	348	375	361	462	387
Mean	314	329	330	372	
	<i>LSD (0.05)</i>				
	N				15
	Zn				17
	N × Zn				35

^aN in kg/ha.